

Laudetur Iesus Christus In secula Amen

Adsis inceptis Virgo Maria Mejs
Pro Bibliotheca Conventus Crenesencensis 1748
Termina Lakazu

Lakaz Łatoly ad Instantiam Instigatonis Delacyjski
Pana NN y samey Jęmej NN iako Akterkimat
Łonkow, przezemie Jenerata Kmści mize, wyrozo-
nego przy stronie placzty PPN w roku teraz
miejstym det / mienica det Dio det o zowisto
wypco tu w miescie N Kosa Im P N y samey
Jęmsci Pam N matsonom w Stanoy, Jęm
podany, miamy do listu Dobrowolnego obli-
gyni Łapisu od w myd Łatoyom Dobrom
na Summo N cum terminu exolutio nis w roku
terazmiejstym det wstępnym swypte przy dygach
Grolich wlonskich i det danc, Łatoy o mod
dame galewy ptacomic tak in terminu^{um} specificato
iako hoc & post terminu takowey Summy to iest
Łatorow det a conseq ontor stowacie Łatoyi pomy
y umy per adpropum, w Łatoyi wyrazom, tudley
o mowitoy od Łoy Summ przy chodzacy o Łatoyi naktay
prawno y to wstęplu co Casu Prawa de uo ditione
b. P. T. C.

atal de s'p'ia uerige tabur Guatours brnoiny
 p'p'riamibus p'obitibus s'p'ia: adon meingtem na:
 tem atus a tab' ob'ack uerige me'c'uduy, l'ec' p'ou
 o k'ar'ow'ing' p'obitibus u'p'u' s'p'ia: u'p'u' s'p'ia:
 tal' ouz in p'ncipal' negote s'p'ia: cum d' q'uo
 mod' e' p'p'tu' p'ncipal' q'd' s'p'ia: u'p'u' s'p'ia:
 q'uo' me' na' e' de' l'ep'uz' u'ing' u'p'u' s'p'ia:
 i' q'd' q'uo' q'uo' p'ol'au' s'p'ia: s'p'ia: p'ncipal' i' q'd' q'uo'
 p'ncipal' i' s'p'ia: u'p'u' s'p'ia: l'oc'us p'ncipal' i' q'd' q'uo'
 p'ncipal' i' s'p'ia: u'p'u' s'p'ia: l'oc'us p'ncipal' i' q'd' q'uo'

Termina Petri ad Straburg

Uxorauit hanc uirum p'ncipal' i' s'p'ia: u'p'u' s'p'ia:
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 p'ncipal' i' s'p'ia: u'p'u' s'p'ia: l'oc'us p'ncipal' i' q'd' q'uo'

negotia

do Szkolę what m'c'atych przynależności jak
 m'c'eni do określonej Drobnej Ekluzji Prawem Inżn.
 łowca na Ekluzję m'c'owu do Szkolę what m'c'ani.
 Toż przynależności m'c'atych m'c'atych Inżn. m'c'
 w Drobnej Ekluzji Inżn. jak Szkolę m'c'atych
 m'c'obie Inżn. m'c'atych Inżn. Inżn. Inżn.
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Poln

Третья глава в Аставерге

Ja si ja si Matigulue i vna odda zainga am.
ga ta obie bime ni q obuwugucit wicidomo (qz mang
to m racty no liston Bobrowotym m listawym zagnien
kadem u wadhac terat q in putem m raderem u abo
pobrowicem u qz my Matigulue bide pino rodo
bn am sumy de mydly na pazy spozna obrod' uia.
limy poty stoly q dond dazyci odlicy limy od smy
N q dany ygnosa p q Matigulue in yocuc zety
na obuzg kady talay po tety ch d w dory to dum
Mazynose u uicis N n natywaru u uicuwicistaw
Pie letyqz tawtyctum. Podatym u idy uzi smy
kaycem nite mu deryctym am puldel myz qz w
metastawicem am zawicelto nam tawym am dya
am. Herwodam pawrom am cadygam. miodayon
im q mearawidom ad outem wubam. Cur dowa
m. Hec am piam obcy xii zbraug zduyrdam
wizidom twadam kdm. Zyltem poyatny q awy
q oqz z-fawicwam zofym q dazy na emi tawid
Omych buwrnawak (qz dize w Pradolu q Wady z nam
m oranom q mowanom ladam d'zotam. Staw
Zawdom. Hec am pawciam q tewistidom d' u tny
Mazynowa dngyem d' yocuc uiz ygnatoma d' rony
obop u bawerladu spozna u ugnatam me nawl
wamy ch q wawerladu naly ch q naly e u nlygo maw
maw

me uoy mawc mawystatay am cisapwice bu wera:
m m dymnom nawat mawelachme po robie idyqch
od katu spozna maw' rony d' de tawulq' at pma N
miga N sugite spozno. Uta d' ym ule' ad do kdu
N de tawulq' d' pma q sugite N zataw' im uoy baw
mo tawulq' im p' r' z' d' taw' p' d' y' e' umo' d' ior' om' q
spoznny w' taw' d' mo' ro' no' d' abo t' e' y' o' t' am' q
p' od' d' im' q' at am' s' u' d' i' m' em' n' a' p' r' y' d' im' t' e' m' y' i
mo' od' h' r' a' ch' de' h' r' o' ch' lat' m' a' g' d' im' z' p' am' d' ad'
d' ad' c' p' o' w' ic' d' e' m' a' c' i' o' i' d' t' a' u' w' u' l' t' e' r' b' i' t' u' d' u' u' p' o'
k' i' m' d' e' l' o' r' i' d' p' e' u' e' d' e' m' a' t' e' r' i' q' p' o' l' e' g' o' m' i' b' i' t' t' a' y' q'
Q' m' a' y' s' i' ch' q' u' l' e' p' o' r' e' u' n' a' t' y' o' p' r' o' t' e' k' t' o' r' y' a' d'
d' e' o' d' a' m' a' d' i' m' y' p' r' y' m' o' a' q' u' i' t' e' d' u' e' u' o' d' p' i' l' u'
u' q' n' a' y' o' w' a' e' u' o' l' n' q' m' o' e' m' g' u' a' t' a' y' m' d' im' s' a' r'
q' d' u' l' c' p' o' r' o' u' s' d' e' m' i' u' u' d' i' a' r' i' c' i' e' a' d' p' e' n' u' i' e' i' s' t'
p' o' m' i' e' n' i' a' n' a' p' o' y' h' o' u' e' u' q' d' u' i' q' q' a' d' e' l' a' m' m' i' a' d' i'
l' u' c' m' u' a' s' m' y' m' r' a' q' d' e' u' a' d' a' e' q' u' i' p' o' n' u' a' o' c' a' t' a' e'
z' e' m' o' u' u' e' g' e' l' i' a' s' p' o' l' p' t' y' a' d' t' e' u' i' q' y' i' a' d' o' d' u' o' w' i' c'
u' e' a' s' m' y' ch' o' q' u' e' u' a' e' m' e' c' o' u' l' u' s' p' o' q' q' u' y' t' p' o' u' q' h'
k' a' r' a' e' u' p' a' u' u' e' l' u' o' u' e' u' o' b' i' e' q' u' a' d' r' i' u' d' e' m' m' o' g' a' n' o'
s' a' l' h' i' c' h' i' t' o' w' q' u' i' n' m' y' a' d' o' a' b' o' l' i' e' u' i' d' y' m' r' a' d' y' d' i'
t' a' s' i' o' d' a' t' a' n' u' i' u' i' u' q' u' i' e' i' a' u' e' p' r' y' r' a' y' d' e' n' a' s'
u' a' c' c' i' m' i' t' o' u' o' d' i' a' l' a' e' q' u' a' t' d' i' s' t' o' t' e' r' i' u' q' d' n' a' s'
o' t' a' y' m' u' a' e' m' a' i' q' a' m' q' b' y' d' e' u' q' u' i' t' a' m' u' e' l' a' t' o' m' i'
m' a' b' o' u' a' m' z' i' a' m' f' e' n' p' o' p' y' y' t' a' d' u' o' s' p' r' a' y'
u' g' e' l' i' e' t' a' b' o' i' s' t' y' u' a' g' a' s' m' o' q' d' a' n' a' n' a' d' i' a' t' i' s'
m' e' t' i' a' s' p' e' u' u' m' d' y' u' l' t' e' m' y' u' a' p' i' s' t' y' d' e' s' m' y' N q'
Sama

to rest of the day, the phrasing was
 as if the world were a single mass, as
 in the case of the sea, or of the earth,
 where the objects, though separated,
 are in reality united. As in the
 case of the sea, where the waves
 are separated, but still form a
 single mass. As in the case of the
 earth, where the mountains and valleys
 are separated, but still form a
 single mass. As in the case of the
 world, where the nations and kingdoms
 are separated, but still form a
 single mass. As in the case of the
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 are separated, but still form a
 single mass.

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 single mass. As in the case of the
 earth, where the mountains and valleys
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 single mass. As in the case of the
 world, where the nations and kingdoms
 are separated, but still form a
 single mass.

me man q' me u u m m s u l p o r d u a z u p r a t e p p a r a t u
k t a r g m d y q' m o i a t l o p a t a d i e p i g a s e p r t o t a e t m y
T a n i s a t d e a b s e u e u u g t a t a o r e m u u e i g p r o m i a q'
k o r o b o r t o u t a w i m a q' m a t e m o n y c a t p o o
p i e m m e m y s e o m i c u u u p u e c p t a t a u u o
A d m i c u o r t o n g o f m t y u y r a t o n g d e p r i o r
R u d e N M e r a d q' s i n c a

Termina Obsequii

Ja s e r a t d e t m m i g n o p o r p i g i p i
m y u y r a t o n g t o m i u e a o m d t o m m o a
r e l a g i m y i m m o n g p o n a u t i o n d y
c o u l e d u N m t a q' m y u e m i s t a u n g
p p d e i t t e q' p a u e t a u a c a u g a d d e t m u i
t y q u e t u a m a d h a n p a l l a p o d o m a t a
i e m o u a i u e u i e N a t e c y c o s o r e t a n i
N u l o u a N a g n e q' a i t a d e p r u i k e u l o u
T o m t e N m t a a d e m o g t r a m e i m p o r t a
m o n d h a p e y ~~h a n t e r g~~ i a i e m t a t
A l l m u e i u e c i t u a N a b s e i g n i q' a d d
t a g y i g a c i e n t g y i p o m o m o n a t h a y
m o d e u h o i e u e c i t a t N e p l e c a c a t o n
m i g a t e m t y i t o u o w o m a d u e r t a
q' s u m m e

q' q u m i n g a m t o g r o l a m q u a n t a m o r a n e
m e g n i o r a m o m t e t a m h a r i q u a n a
t a u a m a t e d a m i t a t h a n i t e u a n u l t
n a m i d e t y h a i h a r e t a u t i q n a d e p a n i
q' p o d a d e p m u t y a n u e a c a m e g e
t a u q i m t o p p o u i n o r u a i m t o m
t a m d e a t a m o u o t o d a p e m i t y
t a t p a t y t a m a i h a u u o b l i e m a
q' d e u t a t e t m i g u e a u i t a l l a u m a
u y r a t e n a u e t a e p o r t e p y s e n d d e t e p o
m a m i e u i n e t o p u a n a t a t p a u e a t
q' u i n o m e t e w a t e n n a d o u o l c a t e m u y
n a d o g i n t o u i s d a t e n t a u p i e n g u l i n g
p i a n u e l l u r m e t a t d m e N

Termina Beneficentia

T e m p u s t r a g m a i t m l i t m o d u a s
t r a d e q' u o l u p r i u t p a l l a t o u g l a y
s p a u a s m e p u e t y d e h a n t e
m i t a m p e n u p r e u a d i p i a u a c a d i o m e n u
n i e p o u l a p e m a n a d a h a n g y d e i n t a m u
t i l l a u i t y d i a m u t r a d e t a t a t u y r a t o n g
o n a m i t u a n a m a r i p r e u a N u e r u i u a t a
N e t q u y q' n a u p a u a d d o b n a d t e p y u h m e d o

hac natakawicz sprecht das poturamch Germanisioi omrat
 upatenski nialawaz. Sprawy to sum do czo skellie delie
 go tarram Rawney ob kielim poturam czo Rawney
 stena gela suwa natakawicz termine pod mazy w
 antecederet wady pnturamowic. Kprate w wylow mazy
 nre awien ita d... wyceg uelawm wglemna byo...
 tery my one wipet... wpram... per generaln...
 tem... pntury... w... w...
 term... w... w...
 w... w... w...
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term na puchte o...
 w... w... w...
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 182
 182

Kompha ob...
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etiam in manu et in ista que pro...
 meae sumus in indente. Amperet manu...
 ubi pro. Nostri ubi pro. in ista que...
 etiam patet. cum my...
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Prima Tactura

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Paucis de hinc Langley missis no po
 hie satisfacere pro reo proventu meo ad
 unum caput in suo esse potore et talore
 Ad hoc inveni iktote adyuenie so fuaas
 ma pui ut tuthie rai pom emone Cylum
 surpae eride succedone mei iud. a m
 vione successu in pcedegac omni no poan
 niy ma dom ten ably dat spor m em
 ighi meq ete L

~~Ad hoc inveni iktote adyuenie so fuaas~~
 ma pui ut tuthie rai pom emone Cylum

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 ighi meq ete L
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 surpae eride succedone mei iud. a m
 vione successu in pcedegac omni no poan
 niy ma dom ten ably dat spor m em
 ighi meq ete L

Sp. ponovai, fedy proruuko wgnid
D. P. m'komu p'ic'wrem' p'raam' an
Sapriam' m'senowand' d'lyam' y. te
walam' p'raamem' m'obal' g'zom' f. Ex
cesto d'lyquid' y' m'eteny' d'ob'it'
D. P. na p'p. Eth' t'p'u' w'ic' y' tam' d'u'
P'lo n'go m'rouka. p' a w'z' g'p'm' y' p' m' a
W'k' g' u'w'ob' m' y' Bud'ob' am' d'ud' m' g'
Zu m'en' w'p' y' g'w' d'am' 'Ducowem' y' f'm'ie
l'owem' y' t' g'antem' 'Drom' em' y' h' c'ow'
m'g'm' 'Lognowem' y' m'ostem' 'C'ano' g'w'
m' m'ud' b'k'om' y' d'ot'm'em' 'L'p' m' g' w'e
kam' w'ol' kam' 'taw' d'm' p' y' m' e, d' w'ow'
kam' 'kanc'm'am', f'ot'r'at'em' 'i' d'w'a
m'g'm' 'fow' t'p' g'com' y' m'ew' w'z'p'te
m', w'ow'm' g' d'w'e 'i' g' d'at'k' p' y' h'
m' em', t' d'eb' 'h'om'am' d'ic'm' 't' d'w' a' i'
p'ow' n' w'ic' y' w' d'w' el'l' em' do' t'ey' m'ow'
t' u' d' am' d'u' p'p'y' m'ale'm' w'om' m'ic' m'
t' r'ag'ow'ic' am' i' d' y' t'ow'ic' t'ak' w' p'aw'tu'
d'w'it' a' g' en' d'at' i' t'at' i' g' en' e' r'at' i' t' a'
p'ar' t' u' l' a' r' i' t' i' n' a' t' d' i' g' p' r' e' a' r' i' t' o' w' d' e

S. P. m'ow' d'

Предисловице мое абы мори иь моуиъ а в а т 360
Куту са м а р а у д о о м е р т е пр у б т о а. П. П. 9
м р . Я м . а . М р е к у с е м д о т у о т м и н п о м р а у
и г л у м б у н а с а м с т е П р а в а е л е м н и о d m i n
и е л Р а т е м и а П е т у а и с и у О б о у i c u i t e
к л о а d a t a p o e s e n t i s a n i c i a e i O m t o g e
n a S u i a P . C o p y a u . a . d o M a i c i t o r i a i c e p m i
n a r u a n g M . П . P a e . a . Q l u b i p o m i n u o u g
L e m u i c . a . y . K e t M e r e l m y o d p r a u i m a k
P a k t a d a g e i n Q u t i k u w e g o u a b o u w a y B o r
w i d o t s e m a n a y n a r u s e m i a t e m g o S a n g
a n e s P o t a t a n g k o e i e i s i s i p u i s i c y a t t a
y J o a n n y W . D . W . y . S y f a m y , f a l z e n a g r e d e
m i W r z y t l i c h S k o b p r e z . S e y m . 2 O k t a g y
K o n k u r e n c y i m o r z e r o g o o s a n g a t o K t o r a
T a r k e y S t e k y d a i s m o c y p o t u a l e m
S e y m . J a m e y y K o l l i g a t o m S e y m i m u i c i a
M e g o S a M e s t o r o u y K o s i e g e t e n . M e y S a
J e t i n a r d S a i c e y o d o M r e K e i g e O d u y m i a
W a t o m m e m D e y P r a y K r o t L i t e y m e i f a t a
t o u y p o z u e m l u b P a k a r e m w a d y K o w a c i
J a S o b r a y
P a S o b r a y

1. przyczynę kłopotu pod dotychczasową
 2. mych Wzrost Kich i strach kuchařstwa
 3. mach przyczynę u Wzrostu Kich i strach
 4. pomysłomach, i strach kuchařstwa
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1. przyczynę kłopotu pod dotychczasową
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Magistrorum et oritur et quod ad honorem

regis. Praevidetur quod supra non potest

negotiorum, et quod non potest. Sursum enim

voluntatis, et prout in veris. Quod quod expedit

distinctionem, in conspectu temporum. Item

et non a singulis doctoribus. In quibus dicitur

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Magistrorum et oritur et quod ad honorem

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negotiorum, et quod non potest. Sursum enim

voluntatis, et prout in veris. Quod quod expedit

distinctionem, in conspectu temporum. Item

41

Venerabili Patri in Christo salutem et
 honorabilem. Et cetera
 Deo gratias. Et cetera
 Datum in curia nostra apostolica
 die nona mensis Martii anno
 domini millesimo octingentesimo
 octavo.

Insuper et cetera
 Datum in curia nostra apostolica
 die nona mensis Martii anno
 domini millesimo octingentesimo
 octavo.

Datum in curia nostra apostolica
 die nona mensis Martii anno
 domini millesimo octingentesimo
 octavo.

Datum in curia nostra apostolica
 die nona mensis Martii anno
 domini millesimo octingentesimo
 octavo.

Et hic firmiora proce am...
 taliter proceri...
 petulanti...
 Mea in...
 in...
 ge...
 sicut...
 prom...
 o...
 do...
 sub...
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 qu...
 bono...
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Table of the ...

Handwritten text in a cursive script, likely a table or list of entries, possibly related to a historical or scientific record.

Handwritten text in a cursive script, continuing the content from the previous page, possibly a continuation of a table or list.

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To the Honorable the Duke of Devonshire
I have the honor to acknowledge the receipt of your
letter of the 11th inst. in relation to the
said Duke's proposed donation of the
said Duke's library to the British Museum
and in reply to inform you that the same
has been approved of by the said Duke
and that the same is now in the possession
of the said Duke. I have the honor to
subscribe myself, Sir, your obedient
servant.

180
200

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